

Design of Regenerative Cooled Cryogenic Rocket Engine

Aishwarya Dhara¹, Pon Maa Kishan², Vasthadu Vasu Kannah³

^{1,2,3} Assistant Professor, Chandigarh University - Mohali.
dharaaishwarya@gmail.com

Abstract

The cryogenic rocket engine using propellants of liquid oxygen (LOX) and also the liquid hydrogen (LH2) category as produces the highest specific impulse has been designed, constructed which comprises of a pressure feed system, injector head assembly thrust chamber, and conical nozzle. This proposed paper describes the design consideration of the cryogenic rocket engine is 1 tonne thrust level low temperature propellants LOX/LH2 mixture ratio (O/F) 5.2 with regenerative cooled rocket engine. The chamber pressure about 35kg/cm². The design philosophy for cryogenic rocket engine parameters and dimensions were calculated along with standardized equation like continuity and isentropic flow equations. The various components of cryogenic rocket performance are calculated using Rocket Performance Analysis (RPA) software like altitude performance, thermodynamic properties, fractions of the combustion products, estimated delivered performance etc. The pressure and temperature distribution inside the thrust chamber and nozzle 2D geometry by GAMBIT and a CFD FLUENT tool is used for investigation. The device fabrication has been done and the results were interpreted with the theoretical model.

Keywords : cryogenic rocket, design philosophy, thrust chamber design, rocket performance, regenerative cooling, computational fluid dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

The rocket engine is one of the engine kind which produces thrust force. The propulsive force is developed because of the nozzle exhaust of the rocket in which the exhaust gas will have a high velocity and hence a large momentum is created which will liftoff the rocket [1-2].

The general governing equation for a rocket engine is given by $F = C_F P_C A_t$

The cryogenic propellants namely LOX/LH2 are used in rocket engines because of higher Specific impulse compared to liquid and solid propellants as shown in table 1. To meet higher payload both for lower orbits and geo-stationary orbits cryogenic propellant engines are used [3-4]. This propellant combination gives higher temperature and low molecular weight resulting in higher specific impulse as survey on various cryogenic engines (using LOX/LH2 propellants) developed by various countries shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Various propellants and its Specific Impulse

Propellants	Specific Impulse
Solid Propellants	265 s
Earth Stationary Liquid Propellants	285 s
Cryogenic Propellants	450 s

Table 2. Survey on various cryogenic engines (using LOX/LH2 propellants) developed by various countries

COUNTRIES	FRANCE	FRANCE	FRANCE	JAPAN	USA	USA	USA
Engines	HM7 A	HM7 B	HM60	LE5	J2	RL10A-33	SSME
Thrust (Tonne)	6.3	6.4	109	10.5	106.4	6.8	213
Specific Impulse, Sec	442.4	444.2	444	450	425	444	455.2
Overall Mixture Ratio	4.43	4.80	5.1	5.5	5.5	5.0	6.0
Combustion Pressure	30	35.5	100	36.8	53.6	27	207
Area Ratio	62.5	82.5	45	140	28	57	77.5
Burning Duration	563	730	580	370	470	450	480
Used In	H8 ARIANE	H10 ARIANE	H60 ARIANE	HI 2 nd STAGE	SII S IV B	CCENTAURS IV	SPACE SHUTTLE

By using RPA software for LOX/LH2 propellant combination for various mixture ratios and chamber pressures details studies have been carried out to find out the performance parameters. The details analysis by using RPA (Rocket Performance Analysis) tool, I_{sp} vs P_c graph has been plotted for various values of chamber pressure P_c ranging from 10 to 100 kg/cm² to the mixture ratio ranging from 1 to 10 and various values of chamber pressure P_c from 10 to 100 kg/cm² ranging the mixture ratio from 2 to 10, I_{sp} vs O/F graph has plotted in figure 1 and 2. respectively. After comparing the result the mixture ratio for the proposed engine is chosen as 5.2.

For rocket engines, higher chamber pressure reduces the size and weight but the structural and thermal problems increase while for low chamber pressure, size and weight go up. Considering these factor, a moderate chamber pressure 35 kg/cm².

Figure 1. Chamber Pressure P_c vs Specific Impulse I_{sp} with various inter-mixture ratio

Figure 2. Specific Impulse I_{sp} Vs Mixture ratio O/F with various pressure ratio

The performance factors are calculated via NASA-CEA code and also with the help of RPA tool for the predefined input values of the rocket engine. Those thermal input conditions are cataloged in tabular column 3.

Table 3. Input Values of Thermal Properties

Parameters	Condition at Injector	Condition at Nozzle inlet	Condition at Nozzle throat	Condition at Nozzle exit	SI Unit
Pressure	3.4323	3.278	1.9266	0.0507	MPa
Temperature	3273.7626	3263.3159	3073.7833	1779.1381	K
Enthalpy	-1061.2372	-1114.0381	-2266.3622	-8177.4259	kJ/kg
Entropy	19.5326	19.548	19.548	19.548	kJ/(kg·K)
Specific heat (p=constant)	8.2606	8.2522	7.3551	3.591	kJ/(kg·K)
Specific heat (V=constant)	7.0753	7.0695	6.3119	2.9228	kJ/(kg·K)
Gas constant	0.6876	0.6875	0.6813	0.6653	kJ/(kg·K)
Molecular weight	12.0912	12.094	12.2046	12.4967	
Isentropic exponent	1.1476	1.1475	1.151	1.2285	
Density	1.5247	1.4611	0.92	0.0428	kg/m ³
Sonic velocity	1607.2926	1604.4777	1552.4959	1205.9266	m/s
Velocity	0	324.9642	1552.4959	3772.5823	m/s
Mach number	0	0.2025	1	3.1284	
Area ratio	3	3	1	8.8463	
Mass flux	474.8145	474.8145	1428.3669	161.4642	kg/(m ² ·s)
Viscosity	0.9877	0.9854	0.9427	0.6194	10 ⁻⁴ kg/(m·s)

Conductivity, frozen	0.5864	0.5846	0.5506	0.3198	W/(m·K)
Specific heat (p=constant), frozen	4.0648	4.0627	4.0217	3.544	kJ/(kg·K)
Prandtl number, frozen	0.6847	0.6848	0.6886	0.6864	
Conductivity, effective	1.6445	1.6403	1.3898	0.331	W/(m·K)
Specific heat (p=constant), effective	8.2606	8.2522	7.3551	3.591	kJ/(kg·K)
Prandtl number, effective	0.4962	0.4958	0.4989	0.6719	

Figure 3. Chamber performance determinations in RPA tool

2. DESIGN METHODOLOGY:

In these proposed design, a conical nozzle is considered because it lets very comfort of the production and also adaptability in changing a present design to larger or lesser area expansion ratio without changing the most of the existing design dimension, where basic input parameters are optimized as Engine [5-6] Thrust = 1 tone = 1000kg = 9.81 KN; Engine Chamber pressure = 35 kg/cm²; Propellant combination = LOX/LH₂; Mixture ratio O/F =5.2; Nozzle area ratio A_e/A_t = 8.8.

For this rocket engine design, 25 degrees of semi convergent angle is chosen, affirmative of a less heat flux and hence increasing the chamber lifetime. The concept of conical configured exhaust nozzle provide to ease the design and fabrication [7-8]. The throat section of the rocket engine nozzle has the circular arc contour with one of the parameter is radius which is denoted by R , The value of radius will be varing from 0.25 to 0.75 multiplied by the throat diameter, D_t . So here it is considered with 0.25 of D_t . A 15-degree divergent split-angled conical nozzle has get on just about a regular since it is a great cooperation on the basis of nozzle weight, dimensions like length, width, and also the nozzle performance [9-10]. According to the thumb rule to avoid flow separation, the exit pressure of the nozzle should not be less than 0.5 of the chamber pressure, so considered $p_e/p_c=0.5$. to find the value of C_F , for the pressure ratio 70 and specific heat ratio 1.213 of LOX/LH₂ propellant combination from the figure 5.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of the comparison with quantities of Mach Number along with isentropic pressure ratio and area ratio in De Laval C-D nozzle section

Figure 5. represents the Altitude Thrust Coefficient vs the nozzle area ratio.

From above graph, taking $C_{f,theo} = 1.72$

The actual C_f is calculate by

$$\text{Actual } C_f = \eta_{sp} * C_{f,theo}$$

Where: η_{sp} is the product of the combustion efficiency and nozzle efficiency (thrust coefficient). The range for corrections factor character velocity is 0.92 to 1.03. Taking $\eta_{sp} = 0.96$, then

$$\text{Actual } C_f = 0.96 \times 1.72 = 1.65$$

3. DESIGN OF THRUST CHAMBER

3.1. Design of Nozzle Thrust Chamber:

We know that

$$F = C_F P_C A_t$$

Where: Thrust, $F = 1000$ kg; chamber pressure $P_c = 35$ kg/cm²; $C_f = 1.65$.

After substituting the values of F , C_f and P_c and A_t yields

$$A_t = (F/C_F) P_C$$

$$A_t = 17.32 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$A_t = (\pi/4) D_t^2$$

Then, Diameter of throat, $D_t = 51$ mm

3. 2. Design of Convergent section of Thrust Chamber:

If the semi divergent angle will go up the frictional losses will be high while the angle is less the frictional losses will reduce [11-12]. The 15-degree divergent split-angled conical nozzle has get over just about a regular since it is a great cooperative on the reference of frictional losses which will affect the weight, length, and performance.

As per calculation, $A_e/A_t = 8.83$

Then $A_t = 17.32$ cm²; $D_t = 51$ mm

$$A_e = 8.88 \times 17.32 = 153.97 \text{ cm}^2$$

Then after substituting, nozzle exit diameter $D_e = 152$ mm.

Figure 6. shows the dimension of divergent section of nozzle.

To find length of the divergent section

$$L_{div} \times (\tan 15) = (D_e - D_t) / 2$$

Length of the divergent section, $L_{div} = 188$ mm

3.3. Design of Convergent section of Thrust Chamber:

If convergent angle is high flow loss will be more while convergent angle is low, flow losses will be less, so the angle ranges from 20 - 40 degree [13-14]. In these proposed design, the convergent angle is taken as 25 degree.

Concept of higher contraction area ratios greater than 5 which have challenges in holding the steady boundary layer, next to the nozzle throat. For pressurized gas propellant feed, engines the contraction ratio values from 2 to 5 have been used. When the shrinkage in-between the engine combustion chamber otherwise noted as the port area and the nozzle throat area will belittle ($A_p/A_t < 3$), the speeding of the high thermal gases in the combustion chamber decreases the effective rocket combustion chamber pressure at the engine nozzle entrance. This pressure drop in the engine combustion chamber leads a small change of magnitude in the values of c and I_{sp} . So in proposed

design Convergent Area ratio considered $A_c/A_t = 3.0$. Contraction ratio $A_c/A_t = 3$; $A_t = (\pi/4) D_t^2$ and $A_c = (\pi/4) D_c^2$
 $A_c/A_t = (\pi/4) D_c^2 / (\pi/4) D_t^2 = 3$
 Where: $D_t = 51\text{mm}$
 By substituting in the equation, yields the value of chamber diameter of 89 mm i.e., Chamber diameter $D_c = 89\text{ mm}$

Figure 7. length of convergent section of nozzle.

To find out the value of length of the convergent section L_{con}

$$L_{con} \times \tan 25 = (D_c - D_t)/2$$

Where: $D_c = 89\text{ mm}$ and $D_t = 51\text{mm}$

Then the value of length of the convergent section, $L_{con} = 41\text{mm}$.

3.4. Design of Thrust Chamber volume:

Designing the engine's combustion chamber with seem quantity of L^* is to be thoughtful since a gain in L^* on the far side of definite boundary outcomes in drop-off of overall engine grouping performance. Combustion chamber volume $V_c = L^* A_t$, In the proposed design coaxial injector is considered, the fuel LH2 allows to recirculate as coolant and injected into the combustion the nature of fuel is GH2 [15-16].

Referring table 4 in accordance to the proposed design, Liquid oxygen/liquid hydrogen (GH₂ injection) combination L^* value ranges from 56-71 cm. $L^* = 635\text{ mm}$ is chosen.

Table 4. Combustion chamber characteristic length, L^*

Sl no.	Propellants used for Combination	L^* , cm
1.	Chlorine trifluoride/hydrazine-base fuel	51-89
2.	Liquid fluorine/hydrazine	61-71
3.	Hydrogen peroxide/RP-1 (including catalyst bed)	152-178
4.	Liquid oxygen/liquid hydrogen (GH ₂ injection)	56-71
5.	Liquid oxygen/ammonia	76-102
6.	Liquid oxygen/RP-1	102-127
7.	Liquid oxygen/liquid hydrogen (LH ₂ injection)	76-102

8.	Liquid fluorine/liquid hydrogen (GH ₂ injection)	56-66
9.	Liquid fluorine/liquid hydrogen (LH ₂ injection)	64-76
10.	Nitrogen tetroxide/hydrazine-base fuel	76-89
11.	Nitric acid/hydrazine-base fuel	76-89

Combustion volume $V_c = 635 \times 173200 = 1297191.09 \text{ mm}^3$

Volume of convergent:

$$V_{\text{con}} = (\pi R_c^3)/(3 \cdot \tan 25)$$

$$V_{\text{con}} = 1/3 \pi (44.5)^2 95.43 = 197894.427 \text{ mm}^3$$

Now let us consider the extended portion of the frustum, to be the small cone

$$h_2 = h_1 - L_{\text{con}}$$

$$h_2 = 95.43 - 41$$

$$h_2 = 54.43 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Volume of the small cone} = 1/3 \pi R_t h_2$$

$$= 1/3 \pi (25.5)^2 54.43$$

$$= 37267.86 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$\text{Volume of frustum} = (197894.427 - 37267.86) \text{ mm}^3 = 160626.57 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$\text{Volume of the cylinder section} = V_c - \text{volume of frustum}$$

$$= 1297191.09 - 160626.57$$

$$= 1136564.57 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$\text{Therefore, volume of the cylinder} = 1/4 \pi \cdot D_c^2 L$$

$$L = 1136564.57 / (1/4 \pi \cdot 89^2)$$

$$L = 182.69 \text{ mm}$$

3.5. Design of Thrust Chamber Coolant Passage:

Mainly two types of cooling techniques are used in regenerative cooled engines. Cooling passages can exist of a construction of circuited close tubes or milled channel inner wall. In the present design milled cooling channel is considered because the surface area to be cooled is less compared to tubular configuration, hence the gas side wall temperature will be less [17-18]. In addition, heat transfer due to fin conduction is available in the case of milled channel configuration. Therefore milled channel cooling configuration is more efficient than tubular one. Because of the above advantages the milled channel chamber are used by most of the countries namely SSME (USA), LE5 LE7(JAPAN) HM7 HM60(FRANCE) C 1, C6, and C12(INDIA).the internal wall of chamber and channels are made of OFHC (Oxygen Free Copper) , Cu-Ag-Zr alloy, CuCrZrTi alloy. In the present design, we have considered OFHC chamber material with counter flow coolant configuration [19-20]. The fuel flow pattern is in counter clockwise direction which is more effective because the heat flux zone is less compare to chamber section [21-22]. So, when the fluid flows anti clockwise over the combustion chamber in higher heat flux zone, the fluid transfers the heat. The methodological analysis of the combustion chamber design is focused on deciding cooling transmission channel with outline geometry, by perusing the constricted number of channel geometry parametric quantities.

Figure 8. schematic diagram of regenerative coolin

Helical transmission channels can give improved cooling system efficiency than the consecutive transmissions, with the disadvantage of larger pressure level drop, but it have the fabrication difficulty also [23-25]. For this investigation we are considering four different helical angles are 7.5° 10°, 15° and 18°. The transmission channel length will be increased accordant to the various angles of helix merely in this situation increases in the angles will effects in drop-off in the definite quantity of transmission coolant channel, so in this projected conceptual design different process of various number of cooling channels N with varying channel width C_w . (C_w / r_w)ratio should keep $0.5 < C_w/r_w < 1.5$.

For this rocket engine plan, the coolant transmission channel with a cross section shaped rectangular is preferable. The count of coolant transmission channel is principally noted by the numerical quantity of boundary at nozzle throat (i.e. minimal transverse sectional of combustion chamber).

$$N = \left(\frac{\text{perimeter of the throat}}{C_w + R_w} \right)$$

Perimeter of the throat = π * equivalent diameter
 Equivalent diameter = (diameter + (2 * shell thickness) + channel height)

(Eqn. 3.1)

Using equation 3.1 various iteration processes have been carried out to achieve the optimum number of channels and channel width as shown in the following tables below.

AT THROAT:

No. of channels	20	24	36	36	48
Shell thickness	1 mm	1mm	1 mm	1 mm	1 mm
Perimeter of throat section	166.50 mm				
Channel height C_w	1 mm	1.2 mm	1.2 mm	1.6 mm	1.1 mm
Rib thickness r_w	7.325 mm	5.47 mm	3.425 mm	3.02 mm	2.37 mm
C_w/r_w	0.136	0.219	0.35	0.529	0.464

AT CHAMBER:

No. of channels	24	24	36	36	48
Shell thickness	1.5 mm	2 mm	2mm	2 mm	2 mm
Perimeter of throat section	289.026 mm	292.2 mm	292.2 mm	292.2 mm	292.2 mm
Channel height C_w	3 mm	3.5 mm	3.5 mm	4.5 mm	3 mm
Rib thickness r_w	9.04 mm	8.67 mm	4.62 mm	3.61 mm	3.087mm
C_w/r_w	0.332	0.403	0.75	1.246	0.971

AT DIVERGENT NOZZLE SECTION:

No. of channels	24	36	36	36
Shell thickness	3 mm	3.2 mm	3.5 mm	3.5 mm
Perimeter of throat section	496.37 mm	497.63 mm	499.5 mm	499.5 mm
Channel height C_w	5.5 mm	6.0 mm	8.0 mm	8.3 mm
Rib thickness r_w	15.18 mm	7.823 mm	5.87 mm	5.56 mm
C_w/r_w	0.362	0.767	1.36	1.49

Table:4 Iteration For Selecting Best Optimum Number of Channels

(Throat section, $d = 2.02$ mm, density $\rho = 8.3984$ kg/m³, $W_f = 0.4802$ kg/sec)
 Coolant velocity $V = \frac{W_f}{no.ofchannel \times \rho \times d \times c_w}$

Table 5. Best optimum geometry of milled cooling channel

Nozzle section	Throat	convergent	divergent
No. of channels	36	36	36
Shell thickness	1mm	2mm	3.5 mm
Perimeter	166.50 mm	292.2 mm	499.5 mm
Channel height C_w	1.6 mm	4.5 mm	8.3 mm
Rib thickness r_w	3.02 mm	3.61 mm	5.56 mm
C_w/r_w	0.529	1.246	1.49

All dimensions in cm
 CHAMBER THROAT SECTION

Figure 9. Dimensions of the throat section (B-B section)

Figure 10. Dimensions of the convergent section (A-A section)

Figure 11. Dimensions of the divergent section (C-C section)

4. RESULTS:

The performance parameter for LOX/LH₂ propellant combination and for a chamber pressure of 35ksc has been worked out by utilizing the computer program in RPA software. The following steady state co-relation in heat transfer from the gases in the combustion chamber to internal wall, from wall and through the wall to the coolant have been utilized to predict temperature:-

$$Q = h_g (T_{aw} - T_{wg}) \text{ (from combustion gas to inner wall)}$$

$$Q = K/t(T_{wg} - T_{wc}) \text{ (through the wall)}$$

$$Q = h_c (T_{wc} - T_{co}) \text{ (from wall to coolant)}$$

$$Q = H (T_{aw} - T_{co})$$

$$H = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_{gc}} + \frac{t}{k} + \frac{1}{h_c}}$$

Where

The design combustion gas temperature is calculated using the following relation:

$$T_{c \text{ design}} = T_{cth} \times (C^* \text{ correction factor})^2$$

C* correction factor is considered as 0.975. Adiabatic wall temperature at various position is measured by using following relations.

$$T_{aw} = T_c \text{ design} \times \text{stagnation recovery factor}$$

The stagnation factor recovery factor is considered as 0.923.

One dimensional steady state heat transfer analysis has been carried out using the same equation used for the thermal design of the coolant channels. The inlet conditions for the analysis are:

Inlet temperature of LH2 (at area ratio $\epsilon = 8.8$) = 28 K

Inlet pressure of LH2 (at area ratio $\epsilon = 8.8$) = 50 ksc

At different locations, the wall temperature, coolant temperature, coolant velocity, heat transfer coefficients, and heat flux are arrived at by iteration method. The results of analysis showing the variation of temperatures (T_{wg} , T_{wc} and T_{co}), heat transfer coefficients (h_g , h_c and H) and variation of heat flux along chamber axis are represented graphically in figure 5.1. The results of the one dimensional analysis for chamber pressure 35 kg/cm², with a mixture ratio 5.2 are given in table 6

Table 6. Heat transfer data for proposed thrust chamber
 (at mixture ratio = 5.2, chamber pressure = 35 kg/cm² and no. of channels = 36)

Location	Convergent	Throat	Divergent
gas side heat transfer coefficient h_g (kw/m ² k)	7.005	18.344	3.143
coolant side heat transfer coefficient h_c (kw/m ² k)	44.657	58.75	21.064
overall heat transfer coefficient h (kw/m ² k)	5.8589	13.462	2.6773
heat flux q (kw/cm ²)	1.5923	3.6764	0.7614
diameter (mm)	89	51	136.74
channel depth d (mm)	1.4	2.02	1
inner rib width r_{wi} (mm)	3.61	3.02	8.06
outer rib width r_{wo} (mm)	3.86	3.37	8.231
shell thickness t (mm)	2	1	3
gas side wall temperature t_{wg} (k)	584	654.4	405
coolant side wall temperature t_{wc} (k)	514.27	605.91	389.486
coolant bulk temperature t_{co} (k)	155	140	33
velocity v (m/sec)	260.41	491.42	48.40
Biot number bi	0.2301	0.2696	0.2297

Table 6: values for MR-5, $P_c = 30$ ksc (426.69 psi), $T_{wa} = 2834.1$ K, Channel width $c_w = 1.4$ mm

location	convergent	throat	divergent
H_g KW/m ² K	6.1473	15.8	3.02
T_{wg} K	448	585.7	332.82
Q KW/cm ²	1.42	3.621	.6626
T_{wc} K	411.59	555.19	280.142
Coolant velocity m/s	322	508.9	58.1

4.1 HEAT TRANSFER CHARTS:

The following are the charts of heat transfer coefficient and heat flux with the results obtained with different axial chamber length. The figure 12 represents the alteration of gas side heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length and indicates that near about 230 mm the alteration of gas side heat transfer coefficient is high. Figure 13 shows the alteration of coolant side heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length and indicates that near about 230 mm the coolant side heat transfer coefficient is high., figure 14 indicates the alteration of the overall heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length. Figure 15 indicates the alteration of heat flux vs axial chamber length and indicates that near about 230 mm the heat flux is high. The chamber at the location $X = 230$ mm is nearly where the heat transfer coefficient starts to reduce.

Figure 12. The alteration of gas side heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length

Figure 13. The alteration of coolant side heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length

Figure 14. The alteration of the overall heat transfer coefficient vs axial chamber length

Figure 15. The alteration of heat flux vs axial chamber length

Figure 16. The alteration of coolant velocity vs axial chamber length

Figure 17. The alteration of gas side wall temperature vs axial chamber length

Figure 18. The alteration of coolant side wall temperature vs axial chamber length

Figure 19. The alteration of coolant bulk temperature vs axial chamber length

Figure 20. shows the result of T_{wg} with different MR and Pc

Figure 21. represents the effect of T_{wc} with different MR and Pc

6. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The rocket engine has been designed to function on a LOX/LH2 propellant inter-mixture ratio 5.2 at the combustion chamber pressure of 35kg/cm^2 with 9.81kN thrust. The design philosophy for cryogenic rocket engine parameters and dimensions were calculated along with standardized equation. The geometrical effects and numbers of cooling channels with rectangular shape on efficiency of cooling are analyzed using four different channel geometries by varying the area of cross-section in the direction of axial. This article gives the details design investigation of reformed cooling for designed thrust chamber. Design results are examined in the form of CAD diagrams.

As a future work, the detail heat transfer analysis of the regeneratively cooled cryogenic rocket will be preceded. In addition to it, the thermal analysis will be compared with the computational methods using Gambit and Fluent Software and the following proposed engine will be fabricating with the help of aluminum sheet materials for technology demonstration.

7. REFERENCE

1. Huzel, D., K., Huang, D., H., “Modern Engineering for Design Liquid-Propellant Rocket Engines”, AIAA, 1992.
2. Coulbert, C., D., “Selecting Cooling Techniques for Liquid Rockets for Spacecraft”, Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, Vol. 1, 2, 1964.
3. Sutton G., P., “Rocket Propulsion Elements”, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 6th Edition, 1992.
4. Batha, D., R., Carey, M., D., Campell, J., G., Coulbert, C., D., “Thrust Chamber Cooling Techniques for Spacecraft Engines”, Marquardt Corporation, NAS-7-103, 1963.
5. Sullivian, J., A., Y., “Numerical Analysis of Variable Property Flow through Rectangular Channels”, The Pennsylvania State University, 1995.
6. Merkle C., L., Li, D., Sankaran, V., “Analysis of Regen Cooling in Rocket Combusters”, Jannaf Propulsion Conference, 2004.
7. Sanford, G., Bonnie, J., M., “Computer Program for Calculation of Complex Chemical Equilibrium Compositions and Applications” NASA RP-1311, 1994.
8. Zucrow, M., J., Hoffman, J., D., “Gas Dynamics: Multidimensional Flows”, vol. 1 & 2, John Wiley & Sons Inc., 1977.
9. Aksel, M., H., Eralp, O., C., “Gas Dynamics”, Prentice Hall., 1994.
10. Bucharsky V., L., “Sıvı Yakıtlı Đtıkı Sistemleri Eđitim Notları”, METU, 2008.
11. Seđkin, B., “Rocket Nozzle Design and Optimization”, M. Sc. Thesis, METU, 2003.
12. Bartz, D., R., “A Simple Equation for Rapid Estimation of Rocket Nozzle Convective Heat

- Transfer Coefficients”, Technical Notes, California Institute of Technology, DA-04-495, 1957.
13. Wadel, M., F., “Comparison of High Aspect Ratio Cooling Channel Designs for a Rocket combustion Chamber with Development of an Optimized Design”, NASA/TM-1998-206313.
 14. Wadel, M., F., Meyer, M., L., “Validation of High Aspect Ratio Cooling in a 89 kN Thrust Chamber”, AIAA 96-2584, July 1996.
 15. Sutton, G., P., “history of Liquid Propellant Engines in United States”, Journal of Propulsion and Power, Vol. 19, No. 6, 2003.
 16. Naraghi, M., H., Dunn, S., Coats, D., “Dual Regenerative Cooling Circuits for Liquid Rocket Engines”, AIAA 2006-4367, July 2006.
 17. Carlie, J., Quentmeyer, R., “An Experimental Investigation of High- Aspect-Ratio Cooling Passages”, AIAA 92-3154, July 1992.
 18. Esposito, J., J., Zabora, R., F., “Thrust Chamber Life Prediction Mechanical and Physical Properties of High Performance Rocket Nozzle Materials”, NASA CR – 134806, 1975.
 19. Naraghi, M., H., Dunn, S., Coats, D., “A Model for Design and Analysis of Regeneratively cooled for Rocket Engine”, AIAA 2004-3852, 2006.
 20. Wang, T., Luong, V., “Hot-Gas-Side and Coolant-Side Heat Transfer in Liquid Rocket Engine Combustors”, Journal of Thermophysics and Heat Transfer, Vol. 8, No. 3, 1994.
 21. N. Shakeel, S. Mehta, and K. Singh, “Experimental investigation on light transmission and structural performance of translucent concrete using 3mm diameter plastic optical fibers,” Int. J. Innov. Technol. Explor. Eng., vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 426–429, 2019.
 22. R. Kumar, J. Singh, K. Singh, A. Kumar, and M. Singh, “A study on effect of operating parameters on tire/road interaction noise,” Lect. Notes Mech. Eng., vol. 15, pp. 631–637, 2014.
 23. E. P. Onyekachukwu, P. Sharma, and J. Singh, “Review work on plastic formwork,” Int. J. Civ. Eng. Technol., vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 1141–1146, 2017.
 24. J. Singh, G. Singh, S. Kaur, and B. S. Sohi, “Performance analysis of different neural network models for parameters estimation of coaxial fed 2.4 GHz E-shaped Microstrip patch antenna,” in 2015 2nd International Conference on Recent Advances in Engineering and Computational Sciences, RA ECS 2015, 2016.
 25. J. Kaur, S. S. Chauhan, and P. Singh, “An improved TLBO leveraging group and experience learning concepts for global functions,” Adv. Intell. Syst. Comput., vol. 741, pp. 1221–1234
 - Huzel, D., K., Huang, D., H., “Modern Engineering for Design Liquid-Propellant Rocket Engines”, AIAA, 1992.
 26. Coulbert, C., D., “Selecting Cooling Techniques for Liquid Rockets for Spacecraft”, Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, Vol. 1, 2, 1964.
 27. Sutton G., P., “Rocket Propulsion Elements”, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 6th Edition, 1992.
 28. Batha, D., R., Carey, M., D., Campell, J., G., Coulbert, C., D., “Thrust Chamber Cooling Techniques for Spacecraft Engines”, Marquardt Corporation, NAS-7-103, 1963.
 29. Sullivan, J., A., Y., “Numerical Analysis of Variable Property Flow through Rectangular Channels”, The Pennsylvania State University, 1995.
 30. Merkle C., L., Li, D., Sankaran, V., “Analysis of Regen Cooling in Rocket Combustors”, Jannaf Propulsion Conference, 2004.
 31. Sanford, G., Bonnie, J., M., “Computer Program for Calculation of Complex Chemical Equilibrium Compositions and Applications” NASA RP-1311, 1994.
 32. Zucrow, M., J., Hoffman, J., D., “Gas Dynamics: Multidimensional Flows”, vol. 1 & 2, John Wiley & Sons Inc., 1977.
 33. Aksel, M., H., Eralp, O., C., “Gas Dynamics”, Prentice Hall., 1994.
 34. Bucharsky V., L., “Sıvı Yakıtlı Đtki Sistemleri Eđitim Notları”, METU, 2008.
 35. Seđkin, B., “Rocket Nozzle Design and Optimization”, M. Sc. Thesis, METU, 2003.
 36. Bartz, D., R., “A Simple Equation for Rapid Estimation of Rocket Nozzle Convective Heat Transfer Coefficients”, Technical Notes, California Institute of Technology, DA-04-495, 1957.
 37. Wadel, M., F., “Comparison of High Aspect Ratio Cooling Channel Designs for a Rocket combustion Chamber with Development of an Optimized Design”, NASA/TM-1998-206313.

38. Wadel, M., F., Meyer, M., L., “Validation of High Aspect Ratio Cooling in a 89 kN Thrust Chamber”, AIAA 96-2584, July 1996.
39. Sutton, G., P., “history of Liquid Propellant Engines in United States”, *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, Vol. 19, No. 6, 2003.
40. Naraghi, M., H., Dunn, S., Coats, D., “Dual Regenerative Cooling Circuits for Liquid Rocket Engines”, AIAA 2006-4367, July 2006.
41. Carlie, J., Quentmeyer, R., “An Experimental Investigation of High- Aspect-Ratio Cooling Passages”, AIAA 92-3154, July 1992.
42. Esposito, J., J., Zabora, R., F., “Thrust Chamber Life Prediction Mechanical and Physical Properties of High Performance Rocket Nozzle Materials”, NASA CR – 134806, 1975.
43. Naraghi, M., H., Dunn, S., Coats, D., “A Model for Design and Analysis of Regeneratively cooled for Rocket Engine”, AIAA 2004-3852, 2006.
44. Wang, T., Luong, V., “Hot-Gas-Side and Coolant-Side Heat Transfer in Liquid Rocket Engine Combustors”, *Journal of Thermophysics and Heat Transfer*, Vol. 8, No. 3, 1994.
45. N. Shakeel, S. Mehta, and K. Singh, “Experimental investigation on light transmission and structural performance of translucent concrete using 3mm diameter plastic optical fibers,” *Int. J. Innov. Technol. Explor. Eng.*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 426–429, 2019.
46. R. Kumar, J. Singh, K. Singh, A. Kumar, and M. Singh, “A study on effect of operating parameters on tire/road interaction noise,” *Lect. Notes Mech. Eng.*, vol. 15, pp. 631–637, 2014.
47. E. P. Onyekachukwu, P. Sharma, and J. Singh, “Review work on plastic formwork,” *Int. J. Civ. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 1141–1146, 2017.
48. J. Singh, G. Singh, S. Kaur, and B. S. Sohi, “Performance analysis of different neural network models for parameters estimation of coaxial fed 2.4 GHz E-shaped Microstrip patch antenna,” in 2015 2nd International Conference on Recent Advances in Engineering and Computational Sciences, RA ECS 2015, 2016.
49. J. Kaur, S. S. Chauhan, and P. Singh, “An improved TLBO leveraging group and experience learning concepts for global functions,” *Adv. Intell. Syst. Comput.*, vol. 741, pp. 1221–1234,